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Inspection and Repair of Deteriorating Systems

By

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Research Article

Inspection and Repair of Deteriorating Systems

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we present the two inspection cycles (Good and Bad) of an optimal control-based framework of deteriorating systems that are subjected to repair and inspection. Two models were compared to ascertain which of the two that predict the mortality rate of transformers. The comparison revealed that the Makeham Model predicts the risk of failure by cause.

Keywords: Maintainability, Reability, Inspection, Gomrertz-Makeham analysis, Meantime to failure, Meantime between failure.

INTRODUCTION

Maintenance planning, based on reliability level of industrial system, is classified into corrective maintenance (CM, actions after system break down) and preventive maintenance (PM, action while system is in operation). Lie & Chun (1986) categorized CM into minimal repair and corrective replacement. PM was also categorized into simple preventive maintenance and preventive replacement. Each of these four activity series influences system reliability. For system (e.g., manufacturing system) output (revenue) to depend on the system performance, optimal inspection policy and ideal adjustment of system state are of essence. On one hand, insufficient inspection leads to some system malfunction and the complete breakdown of the system. On the other hand frequent inspections of system with aim of rectifying defects result in more inspection costs.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

11/KV town feeder transformers located at Gwiwa business unit Sokoto are classified into four sub-feeders, namely: Town feeder, G.R.A, Water works and Industrial.

The number of transformers under each of these sub feeders is summarized in Table 2.1 and table 2.2.

Table 2.1: Sub feeders and their number of transformers

S/No	Name of sub feeder	No of transformers
1	Town	65
2	GRA	72
3	Water Works	42
4	Industrial	46

Table 2.2: 2005- 2009 Town sub feeder

S/N	Year	Capacity (KV)	No of failure
1	2005	100/200/300/500	12
2	2006	100/200/300/500	17
3	2007	100/200/300/500	21
4	2008	100/200/300/500	25
5	2009	100/200/300/500	31
Total			106

METHODOLOGY

The following models Makeham and Gompertz (1986) were compared in the study:

- i. Benjamin Gompertz (exponential)
- ii. W. M makeham (modified Gompertz)

Maintenability models were studied, using these two models.

Transformers under the feeder mode of failure, failure rate, and causes of failures were adopted in the study.
Benjamin Gompertz model

$$f(t) = \alpha e^{\beta t} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

where $f(t)$ is the instantaneous failure rate, α is a constant; β is a time constant; and t is time (in years).
Taking the natural log of both sides in (1),

$$\ln f(t) = \ln(\alpha e^{\beta t})$$

$$\ln f(t) = \ln \alpha + \beta t \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Comparing (2) with the linear equation

$$y = a + bx \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

$$\ln f(t) = y, \quad a = \ln \alpha, \quad x = t$$

Therefore, using regression equation

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sum y &= an + b \sum x \\ \sum xy &= a \sum x + b \sum x^2 \end{aligned} \right\} \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

α and β in equation (1) can be estimated for the 4 feeders.

Failure and Preventive Maintenance Model

For major equipments, such as generators or transformers, the maintenance is carried out routinely every quarter.

Fig 3:1illustration of Maintenance Model 1.

We assume that C_f includes an average value of any additional cost resulting from outage consequences. The optimal interval t_s is obtained by minimizing the cost function.

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum [C(t, t_s)]}{t} \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

The life span of the equipments used in power system application is usually very long as compared with the interval between preventive maintenances. Accordingly, we need to consider only one cycle of operation in developing a model for the cycle. According to lie & chun (1986), the above limit can be approximated by a ratio of the expected cost/cycle to expected cycle length.

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum [C(t, t_s)]}{t} = \frac{\text{expected cost / cycle}}{\text{expected cycle length}} \dots\dots\dots(6)$$

There are two possible cycles of operation_

Cycle determined by the equipment reaching its planned maintenance age t_s and
 Cycle determined by equipment ceasing to operate because of the failure occurring before the planned maintenance time.

The two possible cycles are illustrated in the following fig 3.2.

Fig 3.2: illustration of two Possible Cycles of Operations 2.

Reference to fig 3.2 above, the expected maintenance cost per cycle is given by

$$C_s R(t_c) + C_f [1 - R(t_c)] \dots\dots\dots(7)$$

Where $R(t)$ is the probability that the equipment will not fail before time t .
 The expected cycle length is equal to the sum of the expected length of the expected cycle ($t_s + T_s$).
 The objective is to minimize the total down time or to minimize equipment availability; the cost in equation (7) is replaced by the appropriate quantity.

Construction Of the Maintainability Model

The following notations and assumptions are used in the model:

- i $F(t)$ is the density function of the time to failure of the transformer.
- ii $R(t)$ is the reliability function of the transformer.
- iii T_1 is the time required to perform an inspection. The transformer is not available during this time. If the transformer has not failed, then it is assumed to be in as new state. This may be as a result of minor modification made during the routine inspection and will be considered as a part of the inspection time instead of the repair time.

- iv T_i is the time required to effect the repair. It is assumed after the transformer is in as new state.
 - v P_h is the human error probability for the inspection task. This is the probability that the failure of the transformer will not be detected during inspection. The fact that failure was not detected during one inspection does not change the value of P_h for the following inspections.
 - vi t_i is the time before inspection. The objective is to determine the interval t_i between inspections to minimize availability $A(t)$ of the transformer.
- Figure 3.3 illustrate two possible cycle of operation.

Fig 3.3: Two possible cycles of equation for inspection model.

The Equation for Inspection Model

Using markov model for inspection as in Abdullahi (2009), we have

$$(t_i + T_i)R(t_i) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} P_h^{n-1} (1 - P_h) [(n - 1)(t_i - T_i) + t_i + T_i + T_f] [1 - R(t)] \dots \dots (8)$$

Since $0 < P_h < 1$ the above expression can be written as

$$[(t_i + T_i)R(t_i) + \frac{P_h}{1 - P_h}(t_i + T_i) + t_i + T_i + T_f][1 - R(t_i)] \dots \dots \dots (9)$$

$$= (t_i + T_i)[1 - P_n R(t_i)] + (1 - P_h)T_f[1 - R(t_i)] \dots \dots \dots (10)$$

Therefore, the availability

The critical assumption of the model is that the transformer can be assumed to be as good as new after the inspection if the transformer has not failed or if it was repaired at failure. It may be reasonable and certainly that the time of failure of the transformer is described by an exponential distribution.

$$f(t) = \lambda e^{-\lambda t} \quad \text{and} \quad R(t) = e^{-\lambda t}$$

Where, λ is the failure rate of the transformer.
 Substituting into equation (11)

$$A(t_i) = \frac{(1 - e^{-\lambda t})(1 - P_h)}{\lambda \{ (t_i + T_i)[1 - P_h e^{-\lambda t_i}] + (1 - P_h)T_f[1 - e^{-\lambda t}] \}} \dots \dots \dots (12)$$

To obtain the value of t_i which maximizes $A(t_i)$, we set equation (12) to zero.
 This yields the following transcendental equation

$$P_h e^{-2\lambda t_i} - [(t_i + T_i)\lambda(1 - P_h) + P_h + 1]e^{-\lambda t_i} + 1 = 0 \dots \dots \dots (13)$$

The equation can be solved using iterative method.

Illustrative Example

An electric utility company has to decide on the frequency of inspections and minimal repairs of its transformers. The average statistics indicates that the random failures of a unit occur, on average, once in 500 days and the repair last, on average, 7 days. If the transformer is not maintained, it would fail from deterioration every 1,000 days (on average) and in this case the mean repair time is 14 days. The company estimates that the minimal maintenance would take, on average, half a day.

Assuming that all times are exponentially distributed and that repairs following failure return the transformer to the (...), as new condition determine the optimal maintenance interval with three stages of transformer deterioration.

To obtain the optimal time to minimal maintenance we will apply the markov model, in this case we obtain

$$K=3, \lambda_0=500 \text{ days}, \quad \lambda^{-1} = 1,000 \text{ days}$$

$$N_0^{-1} = 7 \text{ days} \quad N_1^{-1} = 14 \text{ days} \quad N_1^{-1} = 0.5 \text{ days}$$

The state transition matrix.

Where $-\Sigma$ denote the negative of the sum of all the remaining components in row l ,

To obtain the steady state probabilities, the set of linear equations is solved:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} -\sum_1 & K\lambda_1 & 0 & \lambda_m & 0 & 0 & \lambda_0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\sum_2 & K\lambda_1 & 0 & \lambda_m & 0 & \lambda_0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\sum_3 & 0 & 0 & \lambda_m & \lambda_0 & K\lambda_1 \\ \mu_m & 0 & 0 & -\mu_m & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \mu_m & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\mu_m & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \mu_m & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\mu_m & 0 & 0 \\ \mu_0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\mu_0 & 0 \\ \mu_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\mu_1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$P_i A^T = 0, \quad \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} P_i = 0$$

Where, P_i s are the state probabilities.

The equipment is available in state D_1 , D_2 and D_3 ;

Thus we want to minimize the probability.

$$A(\lambda_m) = P_1 + P_2 + P_3$$

The probabilities of interest can be obtained by applying the following recursive procedure developed by Endreyin and Sim (1988) (k is the number of the deterioration states);

Step 1 Set $A_k=1$ compute A_{k-1} from

$$A_{k-1} = \frac{\lambda_0 + k\lambda_1 + \lambda_m}{k\lambda_1}$$

Step 2 for $i=k-2, k-3, \dots, 1$ compute A_i from

$$A_i = \frac{\lambda_0 + k\lambda_1 + \lambda_m}{k\lambda_1} \quad A_{i+1} \cdot \frac{\lambda_m}{\lambda_1} \quad A_{i+2} \quad 1 \leq i \leq k-2$$

Step 3 compute A_{f_0} and A_{f_1} from

$$A_{f_1} = \frac{k\lambda_1}{\mu_1} \quad \text{and} \quad A_{f_0} = \frac{\lambda_0}{\mu_0} \sum_{i=1}^k A_i$$

Step 4 compute P_k from

$$P_k = \left[\left(1 + \frac{\lambda_m}{\mu_m}\right) \sum_{i=1}^k A_i + A_{f_0} + A_{f_1} \right]^{-1}$$

Step 5 compute the probabilities $P_1, P_2, P_3, \dots, P_k$, correspondingly to deterioration states D_1, D_2, \dots, D_3 , as well as the probabilities of the failure states f_0 and f_1 from

$$P_i = A_i P_k$$

Also, compute the probabilities $P_{k+1} \dots P_{2k}$
Corresponding to maintenance state $M_1, M_2, \dots M_k$

$$\text{From } P_{k+1} = \left[\begin{array}{c} \lambda_m \\ \mu_m \end{array} \right] P_i, \quad i=1, \dots, k$$

Applying this algorithm for the case of $k = 3$, we obtain the following expression
For $A(\lambda_m)$

$$A(\lambda_m) = \left[\left(\frac{\lambda_o}{3\lambda_1} + \frac{\lambda_m}{3\lambda_1} + 1 \right)^2 + \frac{\lambda_o}{3\lambda_1} + 2 \right] P_3$$

$$P_3 = \left[\left(1 + \frac{\lambda_o}{\mu_o} + \frac{\lambda_m}{\mu_m} \right) \left(2 + \frac{\lambda_o}{3\lambda_1} + A_2^2 \right) + \frac{3\lambda_1}{\mu_1} \right]^{-1}$$

$$\text{Where } A_2 = \frac{\lambda_o}{3\lambda_1} + \frac{\lambda_m}{3\lambda_1} + 1$$

Taking the derivative of the equation with respect to λ_m and then equating it to zero, we obtain the following equations

$$3\mu_m A_2 - \mu_1 \left(A_2^2 + \frac{\lambda_o}{3\lambda_1} + 2 \right)^2 = 0$$

Substituting numerical values and solving the above equation, we obtain the optimal maintenance interval equal to 158 days.

Estimation of Fitted Models

The estimated Gompertz models using the data obtained from the Town sub-feeder is as follows:

Town Feeder

$$a = -2.5081, \quad b = 0.5313$$

Using (1)

$$\ln f(t) = \ln(\alpha e^{\beta t})$$

$$\ln f(t) = \ln \alpha + \beta t$$

Comparing with (3) above we have

$$\ln f(t) = y,$$

$$a = \ln \alpha,$$

$$\beta = b$$

$$x=t$$

$$\therefore \alpha = e^{(-2.5081)}$$

$$= 0.08142 \text{ and } \beta = b = 0.5313$$

Substituting the values of α and β in the Gompertz model (exponential) we have

$$f(t) = 0.08142e^{0.5313t} \dots\dots\dots(14)$$

Similarly, water works sub- feeder, GRA and industrial feeders.

We believe that more accurate model for future transformer failure must treat the frequency of random events separate from ageing.

H.S.B (1997) claimed that the frequency of random external events (lightning, collision, vandalism) is approximately 0.005 (or 0.5 percent).

Therefore the risk of future transformer failures (due to external events) can be expressed as

$$f(t) = 0.005 + \alpha e^{\beta t} \dots\dots\dots(15)$$

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Computing the above models, the following tables were obtained for the four feeders.

Table 4.7: Gompertz and Makeham Results

Year	Town Feeder		Water Works		GRA		Industrial	
	$f_1(t)$	$f_2(t)$	$f_1(t)$	$f_2(t)$	$f_1(t)$	$f_2(t)$	$f_1(t)$	$f_2(t)$
2005	0.1385	0.1435	0.1619	0.1669	0.1243	0.1293	0.0982	0.1032
2006	0.2356	0.2406	0.2649	0.2699	0.2189	0.2239	0.1828	0.1878
2007	0.4008	0.4058	0.4335	0.4385	0.3856	0.3906	0.3401	0.3451
2008	0.6819	0.6869	0.7095	0.7145	0.6790	0.6840	0.6328	0.6378
2009	1.1599	1.1649	1.1610	1.1660	1.1958	1.2008	1.1773	1.1823

Fig 4.7: Gompertz Town feeder.

Fig 4.8: Makeham Town Feeder.

CONCLUSION

Evaluation/assessment of reliability factor is most important, controlling index for any system subjected to failure condition. In this paper, the model for inspection quarterly was developed. A real world case study was conducted by applying the proposed model.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The analysis shows that Makeham Model was seen to be the better of the two models, as it predicts the risk of failure by cause.

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